

Polarographic Reduction of Isatin, Girard-P and Their Condensation Product

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Polarographic reductions of isatin, Girard P and their condensation product, isatin-Girard P, have been studied in buffer solutions of varying pH at the dme. Reduction of isatin takes place at the β -C=O group through the consumption of two electrons. For Girard P, only two electrons are involved in its electrode reaction at pH > 9, and the compound becomes electro-inactive below this pH. The condensation product is reduced through the consumption of two and four electrons, respectively, in acidic and alkaline media. The nature of the waves, mechanism of the electrode reaction and kinetic parameters are considered.

POLAROGRAPHIC reduction of carbonyl compounds proved that the reduction potential of the C=O group is strongly dependent on the molecular structure of the depolarizer molecules¹. In an investigation on metal complexes of isatin-Girard P and its constituents, isatin and Girard P, it was observed that both Girard P and the condensation product can act as complexing agents while isatin can not². The ir spectra of these compounds³ proved that the C=O groups in them are not identical.

The present investigation is devoted to a study of the polarographic reduction of these three compounds with a view to throw some light on their behaviour at dme in relation to their molecular structure.

Experimental

Isatin and Girard P were B.D.H. products. The condensation product "isatin-Girard P" was prepared by refluxing an alcoholic solution of the two components in presence of acetic acid for 2 hr³. The product was recrystallised from pure alcohol. 10^{-3} M solutions of the three reagents were obtained by dissolving accurately weighed amounts in appropriate volumes of redistilled water in case of Girard P and isatin-Girard P and in 50% ethanol (v/v) in case of isatin. More dilute solutions were prepared by accurate dilution.

The modified universal buffer of Britton-Robinson⁴ was used as the supporting electrolyte. The polarograms were recorded on a Radiometer PO₄ f Polariser. The electrode characteristics were $m=1.973 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$ and $t=4.7 \text{ s}$. The experimental technique and working procedure were the same as described before⁴.

Results and Discussion

(A) Reduction of Isatin (Fig. 1) :

In buffer solutions containing 50% ethanol (v/v), reduction of isatin takes place along three kind of

Fig. 1. Polarograms of 1×10^{-3} M solution of isatin in buffer solution of pH: a-2; b-6.1; c-7.1; d-10.05 and e-12.

waves depending on pH of the medium. In solutions of $\text{pH} \geq 10$, a single two-electron wave is observed. In acidic solutions of $\text{pH} < 6$ it reduces along two waves. At intermediate pH values three waves were obtained. Though the total reduction current is more or less pH independent, the height of the waves is pH-dependent. The appearance of the different waves and the change of the wave heights can be explained by the existence of isatin in different forms, which are pH-dependent. The

presence of the different forms of isatin at different pH was confirmed by an examination of the absorption spectra of this compound⁵. The first, second, and third waves may be assigned to the species I, II and III, respectively.

The $E_{1/2}$ -pH plot indicates that one H⁺ ion is consumed for each electron transfer. The diffusion-controlled character was verified by the linearity of the i_d vs \sqrt{h} and i_d vs concentration of depolarizer plots. The irreversible nature of the waves was

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proved by the shift in $E_{1/2}$ towards more positive potential with increasing concentration of isatin. This was further confirmed by the log plots⁷. The two-electron process for the reduction of the β -C=O group of isatin is probably similar to that found for other ketones^{8,9}:

The α -carbonyl group is rendered electro-inactive, at least before hydrogen evolution, through a mesomeric shift with the neighbouring imine group¹⁰:

The residual positive charge on the nitrogen atom would hinder the charge migration from the phenyl ring to the β -C=O group and hence the participation of the polar structure (C⁺-O⁻) to the ground state of the β -C=O becomes lower.

(B) Reduction of Girard P (Fig. 2) :

Fig. 2. Polarograms of 5×10^{-4} M solution of Girard P in buffer solution of pH: a-8.05; b-9.08; c-10.05; d-11 and e-12.

The reduction of Girard P in buffer solutions of $\text{pH} \geq 10$ gives a well defined two-electron wave.

With decreasing pH , the wave shifts to less negative potentials and becomes less developed. At $\text{pH} < 8$ the wave due to hydrogen evolution vitiates the reduction wave of Girard P. The slope of the $E_{1/2}$ - pH curve amounts to 0.052 volt indicating that one H^+ ion is involved in the rate determining step per electron transfer. In the light of the results obtained for the condensation product and other similar compounds¹¹, the reduction process of Girard P in solutions of $\text{pH} > 8$ may be as follows [path (Ia), (IIb) and (IIIb)]:

In solutions of $\text{pH} \geq 9$, species IIb is the most probable reducible one as in the case of other similar compounds¹¹. Accordingly, the reduction process follows the path IIb \rightarrow IIIb. On decreasing the pH of the medium, the equilibrium shifts to the side of formation of species Ia which is electro-inactive in acidic medium, at least before the hydrogen evolution.

In neutral unbuffered solution (0.1 M NaClO₄), the reduction of Girard P proceeds in one two-electron step (Fig. 4) which may be described by the path Ia \rightarrow IVa.

The C=O group of Girard P in acidic media may be reduced at more negative potentials (the wave joins that due to hydrogen evolution) to those for isatin. This can be explained by the higher double bond character of the reducible β -C=O group of isatin molecule. The lower bond order of the C=O group of Girard P can be ascribed to the possible existence of a hydrogen bond and the possible mesomeric shift with the imine group:

(C) Reduction of isatin-Girard P (Fig 3) :

The polarograms of isatin-Girard P in buffer solutions of $\text{pH} \leq 8$ consist each of a single two-electron wave. At higher pH values, two waves are observed. The second wave is much smaller than the first one. The limiting current attains a constant value below $\text{pH} 6$, then increases gradually within the pH range 6-8. The height of the main reduction wave in solution of $\text{pH} \geq 9$ becomes double that of the single wave obtained in solutions of $\text{pH} < 6$. This means that the number of electrons involved in

can be assumed that both the C=N linkage and the C=O of the Girard P residue are reduced. Since the reduction of each centre involves two electrons and their reduction potential must be different, one should obtain a polarogram consisting of two separate waves of equal heights. This is not the case with our experimental results. The change in wave height (pH 6-8) in addition to the consumption of four electrons in one reduction step may be ascribed to the formation of a new reduction centre which is reduced at potentials very near to those of the C=N linkage, probably another C=N centre. As in case of Girard P, the new centre formed in alkaline media appears as a result of a tautomeric shift analogous to β -diketones¹⁰ (Scheme 2).

Since this keto-enol tautomerism leads to an equilibrium mixture of both the structures, (ii and iii), in which the enolic species contains two C=N centres as reducible ones while the ketonic form exhibits both the C=N and C=O groups, it is possible from the relative wave heights to calculate the proportion of each form in the mixture. Considering that the current of the first wave (i_1) corresponds to the reduction of all the C=N centres in enolic and ketonic forms and that of the second (i_2) represents the reduction of the C=O group in the keto-form, then $2i_2$ = current for overall reduction of keto-form and $i_1 - i_2$ = current for overall reduction of enol-form. Consequently, $\frac{\text{keto-form}}{\text{enol-form}} = \frac{2i_2}{i_1 - i_2}$.

From this relation and the values of limiting current, it is apparent that the enolic form constitutes ~70% of the total structure. The existence of two different forms of this compound in alkaline media is also revealed from the results of spectrophotometric studies in the uv and visible regions⁶.

As in the case of isatin and Girard P, the reduction waves of their condensation product isatin-Girard P at all pH values were found to be diffusion controlled as shown by the linearity in the plots of i_d vs concentration and i_d vs \sqrt{h} . The irreversibility of the reduction process was confirmed by log plots⁷.

Kinetic parameters of the electrode reaction :

The values of rate constant (k_p^0 , at zero volt vs NHE) were calculated for the three compounds using the simplified Koutecky equation^{12,13}. The

values of k_p^0 are smaller than 3×10^{-5} cm/sec indicating that the electrode reaction of each of the three compounds is totally irreversible. The standard rate constant (k_p^0) cannot be obtained for such systems as their standard redox potentials are not known. The values of the activation energies (ΔG^*) were calculated with the aid of the relation given previously¹³. Representative data are given in Table 1. On increasing the pH of the medium,

TABLE 1—KINETIC PARAMETERS OF THE THREE DEPOLARIZERS AT 25°

Compound	pH	Slope (1) mV	Slope (2) mV	αn_a	k_p^0 cm/sec	ΔG^* k cal
Isatin	4	63	47	0.94	2.7×10^{-4}	20.6 1st wave
		71	63	0.83	3.0×10^{-7}	37.7 2nd "
	7	67	47	0.89	7.4×10^{-7}	35.4 1st "
Girard P	10	80	47	0.74	1.6×10^{-17}	96.9 single "
	10	75	52	0.79	1.6×10^{-17}	97.2 "
Isat.-Gir.	4	104	58	0.57	2.4×10^{-6}	32.5 "
		111	58	0.53	6.0×10^{-6}	41.7 "

(1) $E/\log i/i_d - i$; (2) $E_{1/2}/pH$.

the rate constant decreases and the energy of activation increases denoting a more difficult electron transfer and consequently a more difficult reduction process.

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